

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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Bosh muharrir:
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THE USE OF MARKETING RESEARCH IN MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF ENTERPRISES

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Mamatkulova Shoira Djalolovna

Candidate of Economic Sciences,
Associate Professor of the Department of Marketing, PhD
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Abstract: This article discusses the use of marketing research in the marketing activities of enterprises. Several approaches to the stages of marketing research are given.

Key words: marketing research, marketing activities, marketing innovation, marketing strategies, consumer behavior, market analysis, digital marketing, marketing data and research, products and services, market competition.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada biz korxonalar marketing faoliyatida marketing tadqiqotlarini o'tkazish natijalarini tahlil qilamiz. Bunda olib borilayotgan faoliyat bir necha bosqichda tahlil qilinib o'z ilmiy takliflarimizni berishdan iborat bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: marketing tadqiqotlari, marketing faoliyati, marketing sohasidagi innovasiyalar, marketing strategiyalari, iste'molchilarning xulq-atvori, bozor tahlili, raqamli marketing, ma'lumotlar va marketing, tovarlar va xizmatlar, bozor raqobati.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается использование маркетинговых исследований в маркетинговой деятельности предприятий. Приводятся несколько подходов этапы маркетингового исследования.

Ключевые слова: маркетинговые исследования, маркетинговая деятельность, инновации в маркетинге, маркетинговые стратегии, потребительское поведение, анализ рынка, цифровой маркетинг, данные и исследования в маркетинге, товары и услуги, рыночная конкуренция.

INTRODUCTION

In a dynamic and competitive business environment, the effective use of marketing research is becoming a key component of successful marketing activities of enterprises. Technological developments, changing consumer preferences and globalization of markets create complex challenges for companies, requiring constant adaptation of strategies and tactics to maximize results.

The purpose of this article is to consider the importance and areas of application of marketing research in the marketing activities of enterprises. Marketing research not only provides companies with a broad understanding of the market environment, but also serves as a means of anticipating and adapting to changes, ensuring sustainability and competitiveness.

In the course of the article, we will consider the key aspects of the use of marketing research, ranging from its role in forming strategic decisions to application in specific marketing campaigns. Coverage of modern approaches to conducting and analyzing research, as well as their impact on decision-making, will allow enterprises not only to successfully adapt to market changes, but also to effectively interact with the target audience, ensuring sustainable growth and development.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS ON THE TOPIC

Literature analysis for an article on the topic "Using Marketing Research in Marketing Activities of Enterprises" may include the following scientific and practical sources:

Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). Marketing Management. Pearson.¹ - This classic textbook provides a broad understanding of the fundamentals of marketing, including the role of marketing research in decision making.

¹ <https://archive.org/details/marketingmanagem0013kotl>

Malhotra, N. K. (2016). *Marketing Research: An Applied Orientation*. Pearson.² - The book addresses the practical aspects of marketing research, providing guidance on the process of conducting and analysing research.

Hair, J. F., Wolfinbarger, M., Ortinau, D. J., & Bush, R. P. (2018). *Essentials of Marketing Research*. McGraw-Hill Education.³ - This book covers key aspects of marketing research, from research planning to applying the results in practice.

Morgan, N., Vorhies, D. W., & Mason, C. H. (2009). Market orientation, marketing capabilities, and firm performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 30(8), 909-920.⁴ - A study on the influence of marketing orientation on the success of enterprises and the role of marketing capabilities in this context.

Day, G. S. (2014). Is It Real? Can We Win? Is It Worth Doing? Managing Risk and Reward in an Innovation Portfolio. *Harvard Business Review*.⁵ - An article discussing the role of marketing research in managing risks and rewards in innovation projects.

Hitt, M. A., Ireland, R. D., & Hoskisson, R. E. (2016). *Strategic Management: Concepts and Cases: Competitiveness and Globalization*. Cengage Learning.⁶ - A textbook that includes chapters on strategic marketing and the use of research in strategic decisions.

Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2015). *Business Research Methods*. Oxford University Press.⁷ - This book covers business research methodologies, including marketing research.

Grönroos, C. (2007). *Service Management and Marketing: Customer Management in Service Competition*. John Wiley & Sons.⁸ - A book focusing on services marketing, including the use of research to manage customer relationships.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for our paper was structured as follows:

1. Defining the Research Objective: Identify the overall objective of the study, e.g., "To examine the role and impact of marketing research in effective marketing activities of businesses."

2. Formulating Research Questions: Develop the specific questions that the study is intended to answer. For example, "Which marketing research methods are most effective in identifying market needs?"

"How does marketing research influence strategic decision making by businesses?"

3. Literature Review: Review previous studies and literature related to the use of marketing research in businesses. Identify current trends, issues, and gaps in the literature.

4. Selecting a Methodology: Determine the research methodology, e.g., qualitative, quantitative, or a combination of both. Explain why the chosen methodology best meets the objectives of the study.

5. Selecting a Subject: Determine which businesses or sectors will be the subjects of the study. For example, "Service Businesses" or "Small and Medium Enterprises."

6. Identify data collection instruments: Specify the data collection methods, such as questionnaires, interviews, and review of reports and documentation. Explain which instruments best suit your methodology.

7. Data processing plan: Describe the procedures for processing and analyzing the data. For example, the use of statistical methods, thematic analysis, or other approaches.

8. Ethical considerations: Specify what steps will be taken to ensure the ethics of the study, including participant consent and data confidentiality.

9. Quality assurance plan: Develop a plan for monitoring the quality of the data and research results.

10. Research schedule: Create a timeline outlining the key milestones of the study and when they will be completed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As theoretical studies show, most authors assign a central place in the marketing activities of enterprises to marketing research. This is due to the fact that the bulk of the most accurate and long-term information on the market situation comes as a result of marketing research. Marketing research is a systematic collection,

2 https://archive.org/details/marketingresearc0000malh_w4s7

3 <https://zlib.pub/book/essentials-of-marketing-research-bhbsuiptb7k0>

4 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257527431_Market_Orientation_Marketing_Capabilities_and_Firm_Performance

5 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/5568092_Is_it_real_Can_we_win_Is_it_worth_doing_Managing_risk_and_reward_in_an_innovation_portfolio

6 https://books.google.ru/books?id=gc84CgAAQBAJ&redir_esc=y

7 https://www.academia.edu/35725749/Business_Research_Methods_by_Bryman_A_and_Bell_E_2015_1

8 <https://www.wiley.com/en-us/Service+Management+and+Marketing%3A+Customer+Management+in+Service+Competition%2C+3rd+Edition-p-9780470727485>

processing and analysis of all aspects of the marketing process - a product, its market, distribution channels, methods and techniques of sales, pricing system, sales promotion measures, advertising, etc. Therefore, marketing research is a mechanism that links the internal marketing environment of an enterprise with the external environment through marketing information. The variety of connections with the external environment determines a large number of objects of marketing research. For example, in the studies of N. Golubkov, 33 main areas of marketing research are distinguished, and in the work of G. Assel, there is talk about the presence of over 50 objects of marketing research. At the same time, practice shows that any marketing research is complex in nature and it is quite difficult to single out a single area of research. Therefore, usually the objects of marketing research are determined based on the goals pursued by the enterprise from conducting research. To fulfill its purpose, marketing research must provide management with information for decision making.

- The first stage involves identifying a marketing opportunity or problem.
- The second stage involves management developing alternative strategies to take advantage of the identified opportunity.
- The third stage of marketing research involves testing the alternative strategies formulated by management.
- The fourth stage involves management selecting and using marketing strategies based on the research conducted.
- The fifth stage involves research, after the marketing strategy has been implemented, identifying consumer reactions. Tracking sales. In addition, consumers are surveyed to find out whether they are aware of the brand and advertising of the product and whether they are likely to buy the product.
- The sixth stage involves management changing the marketing strategy based on the feedback received from marketing research.

When conducting marketing research, companies face three types of risk: making an incorrect assumption about the necessary research; conducting the wrong research to obtain the required information; misinterpreting the data obtained from the research. In order to avoid these risks when conducting marketing research and to ensure the use of the research results, it is necessary to conduct it strictly. Rigor in research is achieved when the data obtained are valid, reliable, and representative.

Validity is obtaining the right information that meets the objectives of the study.

Reliability is the accuracy of obtaining data. Researchers should try to collect data free of inherent measurement errors. A reliable study should produce the same results when repeated.

Representativeness is the degree that characterizes the totality of consumer output. Researchers are rarely able to interview every consumer in the market, so a sample is usually made that represents the totality, that is, the entire market under study.

Marketing decision making is directly related to the use of marketing information, so the need for marketing research is also based on the content and structure of the enterprise's marketing information system.

The enterprise's marketing information system is a formal structure for the movement of marketing information and its use in the interests of the enterprise. Ordinary information characteristic of the enterprise's marketing information system does not require special methods for its receipt, processing, delivery and use. However, information about the external environment that is not included in the structure of the marketing information system requires marketing research. Based on this, marketing research is aimed at filling the gaps in the enterprise's marketing information system. The more perfect the marketing information system, the fewer special studies the enterprise requires for effective activity in the market. At the same time, it is impossible to completely abandon marketing research due to the unpredictable variability of the enterprise's external environment. Thus, the objectives of marketing research are determined by the need to obtain additional information for making marketing decisions. (See Fig. 1)

Diversification of production and the size of income have a direct impact on the directions of marketing analysis. The volume of research conducted depends on the direction of the enterprise's activities, the prospects for entering the market with new products, and changes in the range of manufactured products. It should be taken into account that any change in the company's activities will lead to the need for a more in-depth marketing analysis aimed at identifying such market segments where the company could maintain its position throughout the entire life cycle of the product.

The process of marketing research includes a number of operations that constitute the stages of their implementation. There are several approaches to the stages of marketing research.

Marketing Research by Evans	Marketing research by E. Golubkov	Marketing research by Assel
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Definition of the problem 2. Analysis of secondary information 3. Obtaining primary information 4. Data analysis 5. Recommendations 6. Using the results 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Defining the problem 2. Selecting the objectives 3. Selecting marketing research methods 4. Defining data collection methods 5. Developing a research plan 6. Collecting data 7. Analyzing data 8. Final report 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Defining the research objectives 2. Situational analysis 3. Developing a research plan 4. Defining the composition of information 5. Developing a sampling plan 6. Data analysis 7. Final report

Fig. 1. Stages of marketing research.

As can be seen from this figure, the technology of conducting marketing research involves two interrelated parts: firstly, the study of external variables that, as a rule, cannot be regulated by the company's management and therefore, for successful commercial activity, flexible adaptation to them is required, and, secondly, the analysis of the internal components of organizations under the control of the administration, and certain reactions of the company to changes in the environment.

It should be noted that the decision to conduct marketing research is made by the management of the enterprise (company) and therefore is subjective, that is, it depends on the point of view and way of thinking of senior management.

Definition of the problem is recognized by all authors as the most important stage of conducting marketing research. The form, breadth and depth of the research, as well as its final results, depend on this.

For example, an enterprise always has an alternative to conduct research on its own or entrust it to a specialized firm; conduct research within the existing budget or allocate special funds for conducting research. In addition, depending on the need to make a decision, objective obstacles to conducting marketing research may arise, such as lack of time, lack or insufficient resources, the presence of relatively cheap information in the materials of other studies, etc.

When defining a marketing research problem, two types of difficulties may arise:

- marketing management difficulties, when certain signs of failure to achieve the goals of marketing research appear;
- research difficulties associated with the requirements of enterprise managers for accurate, reliable and objective information for making marketing decisions.

At the stage of defining the problem, the exact boundaries of the study and the nature of the necessary information about the object under study are established. In specialized literature, several approaches to defining the research problem are often found - analysis of the results of economic and financial activities, expert assessments of specialists, monitoring of the marketing information system, analysis of the production and marketing functions of the enterprise.

After defining the problem and defining the goals of marketing research, an analysis of secondary information is carried out. Secondary information is understood as the final or accompanying results of previous studies concerning a given object, regardless of the goals set.

After defining the problem and the goal of marketing research, methods for collecting data in the process of marketing research are determined. At this stage, scientists do not have a unified opinion. Regarding the content of data collection methods, some authors believe that data collection methods include secondary information analysis and obtaining primary information. Others divide this stage into planning information collection methods and implementing information collection, where information is understood as both secondary and primary information. The next part of marketing research is associated with data analysis. This is the most important stage of marketing research, which depends not so much on the information itself as on the researcher's understanding of the essence of the information. Data analysis can be carried out both by the subjects who conducted the marketing research and by the person making decisions on these studies. Traditionally, the final stage of marketing research is recognized as the preparation and execution of a report on the research conducted. The report reflects not only the actual data that are ready for use, but also recommendations regarding the limits of application of the information presented. In some sources, the final stage of marketing research is considered to be the use of the obtained results. However, in our opinion,

this concerns more marketing influences than marketing research. Based on the above, we can conclude that the problem of organizing marketing research has a multi-variant solution, and therefore ensuring a scientific approach to this problem plays an important role in marketing management.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The study revealed that marketing research plays a central role in the successful marketing activities of enterprises. This research does not simply provide data, but also shapes strategic decisions based on the knowledge of the market environment and consumer demands.

One of the key findings is the need for enterprises to adapt to market dynamics. Marketing research provides tools to quickly identify changes in trends and consumer preferences, which allows companies to quickly respond and adjust their strategies.

The findings strongly suggest that marketing research helps optimize the use of enterprise resources. Allocating funds for research is considered an effective investment, as it allows you to avoid risks and manage resources with maximum efficiency.

One of the key findings is the focus on the consumer. Marketing research provides insights into consumer behavior and expectations, which opens up opportunities to create products and services that most accurately meet customer needs.

It should be noted that modern technologies such as data analysis and artificial intelligence are becoming increasingly important in conducting marketing research. Their use allows you to process volumes of information more efficiently and identify patterns. The study found a need for systematic training of personnel in the field of marketing research. Personnel competence is a key factor in the successful implementation of data-driven strategies.

One of the findings of the article concerns the role of marketing research in supporting innovation. It not only identifies new market opportunities but also evaluates reactions to innovative products and services.

Suggestions:

1. Integrate digital technologies: It is recommended to integrate modern digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence and big data analytics, to more effectively collect and analyze marketing research data.
2. Train the team: Businesses should invest in training their employees in marketing research to ensure a high level of competence and professionalism in this area.
3. Focus on customer experience: It is important to focus on understanding and improving the customer experience through marketing research. This may include a deeper study of consumer feedback and preferences.
4. Stimulate innovation: Organizations can stimulate innovation by using marketing research to identify new opportunities and needs, and by evaluating market reactions to new products and services.

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